

Overloading nitrification systems to accumulate nitrite

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Abstract

Nitrogen removal via nitrite, achieved through partial nitrification and denitrification, allows reducing oxygen and organic matter requirements, enhancing process efficiency. In activated sludge systems when dealing with ambient temperature, nitrite accumulation becomes a challenge as nitrate oxidation occurs preferentially. In the present study, the applied nitrogen load rate (NLR) is chosen as a parameter to evaluate the feasibility of promoting nitrite accumulation in two activated sludge reactors (AS1 and AS2) operated at 25 °C. Ammonium overload was imposed either by applying relatively high ammonium concentrations (AS1, 130 – 570 mg NH₄⁺-N/L) or inflow rates (AS2, hydraulic retention times (HRT) = 3 h). In both cases supplied inorganic carbon (IC) was intended to be limited to 1 g N/g IC, commonly found in areas with soft water. In AS1 nitrite accumulation took place at concentrations of 500 mg NH₄⁺-N/L (0.4 g N/(L·d)) while inhibitory conditions due to free ammonia (FA) and free nitrous acid (FNA) were occurring. In AS2 nitrite concentrations were always higher than nitrate concentrations treating NLRs close to 0.8 g N/(L·d). In this case, inhibitory conditions were only reached for FA during certain operational periods. Thus, in both systems high NLRs seem to be required but insufficient to maintain stable nitrite accumulation and to avoid nitrate limiting IC concentrations and FA or FNA inhibitory conditions for NOB should be imposed.

Keywords

AOB; hydraulic retention time; nitrate; nitrogen loading rate; NOB; partial nitrification.

INTRODUCTION

Partial nitrification via nitrite is an alternative to complete nitrification, to be coupled with partial denitrification for nitrogen removal. When nitrogen removal occurs via nitrite, oxygen needs for nitrification are reduced, with the consequent energy savings, and organic matter requirements for denitrification (Abeling and Seyfried, 1992), as well. Not only nitrite accumulation is targeted, but also its conversion limited to 50% for coupling to subsequent anammox process (Van Loosdrecht and Jetten, 1998). Successful nitrite accumulation by ammonia-oxidizing bacteria (AOB) activity requires the imposition of appropriate operating conditions to prevent nitrite oxidation to nitrate by nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (NOB). Thus, understanding those conditions that promote nitrite oxidation is compulsory to find the way to avoid nitrate production. Several operational conditions have been tested to obtain this nitrite accumulation. Among these conditions, the inhibition of NOB by free ammonia (FA) or free nitrous acid (FNA) (Pedrouso et al., 2017) or nitrogen overload conditions (Chenjie et al, 2025) have been explored. This study aims at evaluating the effect of ammonium overloads on the accumulation of nitrite, in two nitrification activated sludge systems operated at 25 °C, by fixing the ammonium concentration and the inflow rate, respectively.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Two activated sludge systems (AS1 and AS2) were used comprising each a reactor of 2 L and a

settler of 1 L. AS1, which has a relatively high hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 24 h (Table 1) was fed with a single peristaltic pump, while AS2 was equipped with two peristaltic pumps, one for the addition of the concentrated feeding solution and the other for the dilution water. The effluent was discharged from the settler by overloading. In both systems, two blowers were used to supply oxygen to the reactor and to recirculate sludge from the settler to the reactor with a mammoth pump, respectively. The temperature was maintained at 25 °C in a thermostatic chamber. No pH or DO control was installed. The DO concentration was always over 5 mg O₂/L in both reactors, avoiding the effects of DO limitation in the study. Both reactors were inoculated with activated sludge from a wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) located in Galicia. The feeding contained variable concentrations of ammonia nitrogen (Table 1) with a nitrogen-to-inorganic carbon (N/IC) ratio of 1 g/g.

Table 1. Operational conditions for AS1 and AS2.

Parameter	Units	AS1	AS2
Days of operation	day	66	108
NH ₄ ⁺	mg N/L	130 – 570	15 - 200
NLR	g N/(L·d)	0.14 - 0.61	0.12 – 0.78 (1.57*)
HRT	H	24	3

* Nitrogen loading rate (NLR) corresponding to a mistake in the influent preparation.

The specific nitrogen loading rate (SNLR) was calculated as the amount of NH₄⁺-N fed per biomass contained inside the reactor per day. The NO₂⁻/NO_x⁻ ratio was determined as the nitrite accumulated divided by the nitrite and nitrate produced. FA and free nitrous acid FNA concentrations were estimated based on the equations proposed by Anthonisen et al. (1976).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ammonium oxidation performance

Ammonium oxidation to nitrite and/or nitrate took place immediately after both reactors inoculation and remained on average at 53% and 45% in AS1 and AS2, respectively. In the case of AS1, in the period fed with 400 mg NH₄⁺-N/L nitrite was the main nitrogen oxide compound accumulated with concentrations of 170 mg NO₂⁻-N/L (Fig. 1a). However, nitrate concentration increased progressively and was the only oxidised compound accumulated achieving concentrations of 220 mg NO₃⁻-N/L when the feeding contained 500 mg NH₄⁺/L. In the case of AS2, the nitrite concentration averaged 25 mg NO₂⁻-N/L (except in the ammonium overload period between days 45 to 49), remaining always above the nitrate concentration (Fig.1b). Nitrate was present during the entire operational period at average concentrations of 20 mg N/L. In both reactors, biomass concentrations ranged from 50 to 180 mg VSS/L (AS1) and from 45 to 330 mg VSS/L (AS2), as they depended on the solids recycling efficiency and washout from the settler that is more challenging when shorter HRT are applied.

Parameters affecting nitrite accumulation

Results from both systems were compared to understand those parameters that could influence the ammonium conversion to nitrite. In this sense, the applied NLR of 440 mg NH₄⁺/(L·d) (Fig. 1a) allowed the accumulation of approximately 233 mg NO₂⁻/(L·d) in AS1, while in AS2 at 470 mg NH₄⁺/(L·d) (Fig. 1b) the oxidation to nitrite was of 211 mg NO₂⁻/(L·d). Thus, the nitrite produced loads were very similar in both reactors.

Figure 1. Evolution over time of the concentrations of NH_4^+ (mg N/L) influent (●) and effluent (○), NO_2^- (□) effluent and NO_3^- (△) effluent, and applied NLR (◆) in AS1 (a) and AS2 (b); evolution over time of FA (●) and FNA (□) concentrations (mg N/L) in AS1 (c) and AS2 (d) (horizontal red lines correspond to the lowest FA and FNA concentrations which cause inhibition of NOB activity); evolution of the ratio $\text{NO}_2^-/\text{NO}_x^-$ (●) (g/g) and the percentage of ammonium oxidized to nitrite and nitrate (△) in AS1 (e) and AS2 (f) versus the SNLR (g N/(g VSS·d)).

To explain this behaviour, FA and FNA concentrations were calculated for both reactors (Fig. 1c and 1d). Results in both reactors indicated that AOB were never inhibited, as FA and FNA concentrations remained below the reported inhibitory thresholds of 10-150 mg FA/L (Anthonisen et al., 1976) and 0.4-0.63 mg FNA/L (Valdivelou et al., 2007) (Fig. 1c and 1d). On the contrary, in AS1, both FA and FNA concentrations exceeded the minimum inhibitory values for NOB of 0.1-1.0

mg FA/L (Anthonisen et al., 1976) and 0.022-0.22 mg FNA/L (Zhou et al., 2011) while feeding 130 and 400 mg $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N/L}$. However, the increase in NLR (570 $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N/L}$) in AS1 did not result in the accumulation of more nitrite that slowly decreased while the reactor entered a period where only FA inhibitory conditions were reached. In this period the excess of inorganic carbon supply (up to 38 mg IC/L), caused the increase of pH and the FNA concentration drop, provoking the oxidation to nitrate. Simultaneously, the measured biomass concentration decreased from 114 to 70 mg VSS/L. In the conditions of AS2, most of the operational time the inhibition of NOB could happen due to FA concentrations, while FNA concentrations were never high enough. However, a mixture of nitrite and nitrate was always present in the effluent while part of the ammonium remained. In this reactor, IC concentrations were always present in the effluent (1 - 27 mg IC/L). Biomass concentrations varied in all the period between 45 - 330 mg VSS/L.

In both reactors applied NLRs were higher than those used by Jia et al. (2025) of 0.33 g N/(L·d) which caused complete inhibition of ammonium oxidation. Increasing the applied SNLR did not significantly affect the percentage of ammonium oxidized to nitrite and nitrate in both reactors (Fig. 1e & 1f). However, in AS1, the ratio nitrite/oxidized ammonium decreased from 0.90 to 0.09 g $\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N/g NO}_x^-\text{-N}$ while in AS2 it remained on average at 0.57 g $\text{NO}_2^-\text{-N/g NO}_x^-\text{-N}$ up to values of 20 g N/(g VSS·d).

CONCLUSIONS

Nitrite accumulation is not possible by only controlling the applied NLR. Its effect must be coupled with IC limitation and the inhibitory effects of FA or FNA over NOB. Imposing high SNLR initiates nitrite accumulation and helps maintain a stable percentage of nitrite produced over total oxidized ammonium. However, it is not the only parameter affecting the obtained $\text{NO}_2^-/\text{NO}_x^-$ ratio. Further research is needed to determine the maximum NLR and optimal operational conditions that allow for the ammonium conversion mainly to nitrite.

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